

ANALYSIS OF THE COMPRESSION FATIGUE PROPERTIES OF A GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITE

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An analytical study was made of an extensive set of experimental fatigue data consisting of unidirectional, $[\pm 45]_{ns}$ and $[0_{16}/(\pm 45)_5/90_4]_c$ laminates of Hercules AS/3501-6 graphite/epoxy. Both dry and moisture-preconditioned specimens were tested at room temperature and elevated temperature. The analysis included scanning electron microscopy as well as detailed finite element micromechanical modeling and application of classical lamination theory.

The scanning electron microscopy study disclosed the presence of extensive fiber-matrix debonding, longitudinal cracking, ply delaminations, and fiber micro-buckling. Relatively few differences were observed between static compression failure modes and compression fatigue failure modes.

Using this micromechanics analysis to determine the local stress states for the various combinations of temperature, moisture and loading mode, predictions of probable failure sequences were made. Comparisons between theory and experiment were generally in reasonable agreement.

INTRODUCTION

A joint study was conducted by the Composite Materials Research Group at the University of Wyoming and Northrop Corporation, sponsored by the U.S. Naval Air Systems Command. Reference [1] is a complete report of this joint program. All test specimens were then forwarded to the University of Wyoming for detailed analysis. Particular emphasis was on deriving an adequate understanding of static test results, as a necessary initial step toward the ultimate goal of being able to analyze and predict compression fatigue response. A thorough survey of the literature was conducted initially, primarily to catalogue the fatigue damage and failure modes observed in prior studies.

Although there is a significant amount of fatigue data for composite materials in the literature, most of the data represent tension-tension loadings; and much of the remainder are for tension-compression loadings. For example, the ASTM Symposium on Fatigue of Filamentary Composite Materials, held in late 1976 [2], contained no papers devoted to compression-compression fatigue. The most recent ASTM symposium on the same topic, held in May 1979 [3], did contain two papers related to the subject. Both the Navy [4,5] and NASA [6] have generated interest in compression-compression fatigue during the past several years, the Navy expressing a particular emphasis on compression-compression fatigue of impact-damaged composites [7]. The NASA-sponsored work of Reference [8] stressed the analysis of fatigue of notched composites. The present study was another attempt to define failure initiation due to compression-compression fatigue. Early works were for glass/epoxy composites rather than graphite/epoxy; Reference [9] represents one such study, and contains a literature survey of compression fatigue up to 1972. Most of this early work was directed toward generating experimental data rather than attempting to develop a fatigue theory, or to study failure mechanisms. Even more recently, the tendency has been to take this same approach. For example, Ryder and Walker [10], in an extensive study sponsored by the Air Force Materials Laboratory through late 1976 to determine the effect of compressive loading on the fatigue lifetime of graphite/epoxy laminates, stated that primary emphasis of the program was on the accumulation of a statistically significant data base; a general model with capability to account for compressive loading was not attempted. Correspondingly, while Reference [10] lists almost 70 references, few are related to compressive fatigue; and Reference [10] itself only considered tension-tension and tension-compression fatigue. Yang [11] used the experimental data of Reference [10] for tension-compression fatigue to verify his simple theory of residual strength degradation. His approach is phenomenological, and based upon statistical methods.

Physical rather than phenomenological approaches to understanding compression fatigue appear to have greater promise. That is, by observing what is actually physically happening to the composite during the fatigue loading, or by studying the details of the fracture surfaces subsequent to failure, it is anticipated that the causes and mechanisms of failure can be identified. A number of investigators have taken this approach. A good review of work in this area up to 1973 has been presented by Dew-Hughes and Way [12]. While not addressing compression fatigue specifically, they do make a number of interesting observations, and list many references to related studies. They concluded that fatigue damage in composites generally occurs in the following sequence: local debonding of the fiber/matrix interface (crack initiation), the joining up of locally debonded regions (crack propagation along the interface), crack propagation through the matrix, fracture of fibers and final failure. They, of course, recognized occasional variations to this sequence, depending upon type of laminate and loading. Assuming that interface debonding exposes the fibers to the environment and thus compromises the long term integrity of the composite, they further concluded that the onset of debonding marks the useful limit of the composite and thus S-N curves should show cycles to start of debonding, not cycles to failure. While perhaps somewhat severe, it does point up one additional aspect that is unique to composites, the problem of moisture absorption.

Salkind [13], reviewing essentially the same time period as Reference [12], but from a different perspective, nevertheless came to a similar conclusion, viz, the limiting factor in fatigue is the interface. Over 80 references are listed to support his discussion. Salkind also suggests an alteration of the traditional method

of presenting fatigue data. In addition to plotting the number of cycles to fracture on the S-N plot, as is conventionally done, he suggests plotting curves which represent various percentage changes in stiffness of the composite material. That is, this phenomenological observation of progressive damage is an indicator of the actual physical degradation in the composite.

Kunz and Beaumont [14] did look specifically at the physical aspects of compression fatigue, for both unidirectional and cross-plyed graphite/epoxy composites. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of fatigue failures led to their conclusion that axial cracking is the primary fracture mechanism in unidirectional composites, and splitting within and between transverse plies is instrumental in promoting crack extension in cross-plyed composites. They stated that prevention of these microfracture processes could be achieved by a high interfacial shear strength. Kunz and Beaumont also discuss microbuckling of fibers in 0° plies as a failure mode. Local fiber buckling has been observed by many investigators, for both static and fatigue loadings in compression; fiber buckling was prominent in the present study also, as will be discussed later.

Since relatively little has been achieved to date in identifying the physical mechanisms responsible for compression-compression fatigue, it is logical to look to the corresponding literature for static compression of composites. Orringer [15] presents a good survey of the literature to 1971, as well as an excellent discussion of the mechanisms of compressive failure, both from an analytical and an experimental viewpoint. The experimental models Orringer fabricated and tested were macro models, consisting of 1.6 mm (0.063") diameter steel piano wires or 2 mm (0.079") glass rods cast in various arrays in a transparent polymer matrix. Such models permit ready visualization of the failure sequence and have been used by a number of investigators, including Greszczuk [16,17], to study fiber microbuckling. Reference [16], in addition to presenting a good survey of the literature, also references most of Greszczuk's extensive prior work in this area, as does Reference [17]. Greszczuk states that compression failure can occur by transverse tensile failure or fiber-matrix debonding prior to microbuckling, this failure mode resulting from transverse tensile stresses (normal to the direction of the fibers) which are induced in a composite subjected to compression loading in the fiber direction as a result of the differences between the Poisson's ratio of the fibers and the matrix. That is, while the ultimate failure is fiber microbuckling, it is governed by the fiber-matrix bond strength. Note that this is essentially the same conclusion reached in References [12-14] for fatigue loadings, as previously discussed. Greszczuk also states that another factor influencing the load level at which microbuckling failure occurs in a static compression test is the inelastic and nonlinear behavior of the matrix.

For these reasons, viz, the importance of the interface stresses and the influence of matrix nonlinear stress-strain response, the University of Wyoming's Micro-mechanics analysis [18,19] was ideally suited for use in the present study, and was used extensively.

In addition to the experimental study of macro models, several investigators have sectioned and examined actual composites after static compressive loadings. Of particular significance is the work of Hancox in this area. In Reference [20] he presents a good literature survey, as well as photomicrographs indicating local fiber failures in graphite/epoxy composites, including evidences of fiber microbuckling. It was, in fact, to explore in detail the physical failure phenomena associated with compression-compression fatigue that extensive SEM work was done in the present study.

SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY

The scanning electron microscope (SEM) is an excellent tool for use with composite materials because of its good depth of field, wide range of magnification, and built-in photography capability. A total of 59 specimens were mounted and examined, to provide a thorough representation of the failure modes associated with the various laminates, loading modes, and environmental conditions. Specimens were chosen with respect to type of gross failure, and loading history. For example, for

fatigue observations, specimens that sustained high loads for large numbers of cycles were selected wherever possible, rather than to examine residual strength specimens, because it was felt that the residual strength tests might have introduced extraneous failure modes. All SEM work, from mounting the specimens to taking the photographs, was personally conducted by the author and his colleagues, in an effort to maximize their understanding of the phenomena observed.

Wherever possible, the actual fracture surface was examined directly. If reasonably intact, and not excessively shattered, these yielded very useful information. For fracture surfaces perpendicular to the axis of loading, the surface was sometimes too irregular, or too crushed, for satisfactory observation. In these cases, a very light cut was made parallel to the fracture surface, to expose the structure, or a cut was made perpendicular to the fracture surface (parallel to the loading axis), to expose any damage below the surface.

The failures were of several types, with three general modes predominating. The first was debonding of the fibers from the matrix material within a given ply, as indicated in Figure 1. This typically led to longitudinal, transverse or shear cracks, and total failure. The second mode was debonding at the ply interfaces, Figure 2. This was especially pronounced in the $[\pm 45]$ laminates, because of the high interlaminar shear stresses developed at these interfaces. The third mode of failure represents a type of column instability problem. When the fibers buckle (bend), being relatively brittle materials they break, often shattering into several segments, as seen in Figure 3.

It is difficult to determine from the SEM observations which of the several failure modes occurred first in any given test. In particular, it is not clear if the graphite fibers buckled locally causing them to pull away from the matrix, or if the interface debonding occurred first. At this point, however, the latter appears more likely. This is evidenced in the unidirectional specimen tests where large numbers of longitudinal splits occurred even when buckling was not observed.

Some general trends can be noted. In the unidirectional longitudinal static compression specimens, extensive microbuckling was observed. This appeared to be coupled in many cases to longitudinal splits. In the unidirectional longitudinal compression fatigue specimens, many more longitudinal splits were observed, but microbuckling was far less pronounced. Buckling on a macro scale was observed frequently. However, this is suspected to have been caused by the prior occurrence of the longitudinal splits, which caused a loss of overall stability of the composite.

The $[\pm 45]$ static and fatigue specimens exhibited mutually similar modes of failure. This may have been due to the dominance of the interlaminar failures induced by the very high interlaminar shear stress in these $[\pm 45]$ laminates. Axial splits within individual plies were infrequent.

Figure 1
Static Longitudinal Compression of a Unidirectional Composite in a Room Temperature, Wet Condition (Transverse Saw-Cut Plane Close to Fracture Surface).

The complex laminate, as might be expected, exhibited most of the observed modes of failure. However, delaminations between plies were observed more frequently than any other failure mode, and axial splits within individual plies were non-existent. The presence of the 90° plies, not present in any of the other laminates, may have influenced this response.

Throughout the entire SEM study, the influence of moisture or elevated temperature was not observed. No obvious differences were noted in the corresponding failure surfaces.

MICROMECHANICS ANALYSIS

Both the literature survey and the subsequent SEM observations indicated that the state of stress in the matrix material surrounding individual fibers, and in particular the normal and shear stresses at the fiber-matrix interface, may have a dominant influence on the response of even a complex laminate when subjected to compression. As the literature survey clearly indicated, static compression of composite materials is not yet adequately understood, and much less is known about compressive fatigue. Thus, the first step is to understand static compression. The University of Wyoming's Micromechanics analysis provides an excellent tool for this purpose since it contains many advanced features not available in most other analyses. These are described in detail in Reference [6,19].

The Micromechanics analysis is a generalized plane strain displacement formulation of the boundary value problem represented by one or more fibers contained in a repeating unit of matrix material. For the present study, the stresses in and around a circular fiber in a square packing array were studied. The fiber is assumed to remain linearly elastic, but can be anisotropic (transversely isotropic). The matrix material is assumed to be

Figure 2
Longitudinal Compressive Fatigue of a $[\pm 45]_6$ Laminate in a Room Temperature, Dry Condition (Stress Applied Along Vertical Axis; Fracture Surface Parallel to Laminate Plane).

Figure 3
Static Longitudinal Compression of a $[0_{16}/\pm(45)_5/90_4]_C$ Laminate in a Room Temperature, Wet Condition (Load Applied Along Vertical Axis; Delamination Fracture Surface Parallel to a 0° Ply).

elastoplastic (i.e., it can exhibit any nonlinear stress-strain response), but isotropic. The actual experimentally measured stress-strain response of the epoxy matrix was input to the program. The analysis considers temperature- and moisture-dependent material properties. While not important to the graphite fiber of the present study, this feature is of major importance in modeling the epoxy matrix response, as will be seen.

Being an inelastic analysis, it models the loadings in small increments. The material properties can thus be adjusted within each increment. Normal loading increments in all three principal coordinate directions, i.e., along the fiber axis and in two orthogonal directions, and also increments of temperature change and moisture content change can be specified for each increment. The analysis handles elastic unloading as well as elastoplastic loading; thus, the loading does not have to be monotonic, i.e., any sequence of incremental values can be specified.

A Prandtl-Reuss flow rule is used to model the inelastic material behavior, and octahedral shear stress-octahedral shear strain yield and failure criteria are incorporated, along with a supplemental principal stress failure criterion.

The computer plot routine is capable of providing, for each loading increment, contour plots of any or all of the following quantities: principal stresses σ_1 , σ_2 , σ_z , transverse shear stress, octahedral shear stress, octahedral shear strain, and the normal and shear stress distributions around the fiber-matrix interface. The composite stress-strain response in any of the three loading directions can be plotted, or the octahedral shear stress-octahedral shear strain response of any element can be plotted increment by increment on the input set of curves for that constituent. Several of these plot capabilities were used in the present study.

FIBER AND MATRIX PROPERTIES

The Hercules AS graphite fibers and Hercules 3501-6 epoxy matrix were modeled using the properties given in Table 1.

Hercules AS Graphite Fiber Properties [21]

Tensile Strength σ_L^U , MPa (ksi)	Longitudinal Modulus E_L , GPa (Msi)	Transverse Modulus E_T , GPa (Msi)	Major Poisson's Ratio* ν_{LT}	In-Plane Poisson's Ratio* ν_{TT}	Coefficients of Thermal Expansion	
					Longitudinal $10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{F}$)	Transverse $10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{F}$)
3100 (450)	220 (32)	13.8 (2.0)	0.20	0.25	-0.36 (-0.20)	18 (10)

*Estimated Values [22,23]

Hercules 3501-6 Epoxy Matrix Properties at Room Temperature [24]

Young's Modulus, E_m	4.3 GPa (0.62 Msi)
Tensile Strength, σ_m^U	83 MPa (12 ksi)
Poisson's Ratio, ν_m	0.34
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion, α_m	$40 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($22.2 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{F}$)
Coefficient of Moisture Expansion, β_m	$2 \times 10^{-3}/\%$

Table 1: Constituent Material Properties

The matrix properties were actual experimental data generated at the University of Wyoming [24]. The values listed in Table 1 are room temperature values. Since the epoxy stress-strain response varies significantly with both temperature and moisture, it is necessary to characterize the unreinforced resin over the entire temperature and moisture ranges of interest, generating a whole family of stress-strain curves in the process. This was done, some typical results being indicated in Figure 4. The influence of moisture content M at two extremes of the temperature range of interest is shown. Although octahedral shear stress-octahedral shear strain curves are shown in Figure 4, the uniaxial tensile stress-strain curves have the same general shapes. In fact, the results shown were generated using uniaxial tensile tests. No compressive test results were available for use in the present study.

MICROMECHANICS PREDICTIONS VERSUS EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Since the Micromechanics analysis predicts the complete composite response of a unidirectional ply, and the local stress state around an individual fiber in any laminate, it was most informative to analyze the response of the unidirectional laminate. This is because although the local stresses are not measured experimentally, the composite stiffness and strength properties are. Thus, direct comparisons can be made with the unidirectional composite data, and the strength of these composites can be related to the predicted internal stress states. In the present study, where compressive loadings were of primary concern, the fiber-matrix interface stresses were of particular interest. As noted in the literature survey and in the discussion of SEM observations, debonding appears to be a possible cause of compressive failure.

The unidirectional composite specimens subjected to static loadings were in one of two preconditioning states, viz, dry or wet, and tested at either room temperature or 103°C (218°F), resulting in four different sets of conditions. Both longitudinal and transverse tests were conducted in compression in all cases. In addition, static tensile tests were also conducted under room temperature dry conditions. All ten cases were modeled using the Micromechanics computer program.

These results are summarized in Tables 2 and 3. As can be seen, the predicted stiffness values, i.e., modulus and Poisson's ratio, are in reasonable agreement with the experimental averages.

The Micromechanics analysis does not adequately predict composite failure at present, for reasons which are reasonably well understood, and discussed in later paragraphs. It does an adequate job for axial tension, which is governed primarily by fiber tensile fracture, but predicts values which are too high by about 75 percent for axial compression, due basically to the fact that it does not include fiber microbuckling as a possible failure mode. Transverse tensile failure is over predicted by about a factor of two, possibly due to lack of an adequate failure theory, while transverse compression is underpredicted by somewhat more, due to the fact that at present only first failure is predicted. In compression, a microcrack does not propagate as readily as in tension. Thus, the composite can carry much more applied stress before total failure occurs. Obviously, more work needs to be done to develop theoretical composite strength predictions.

An important contribution of the Micromechanics analysis is the prediction of the variations of the internal stresses

Figure 4
Hercules 3501-6 Epoxy Matrix Properties
as a Function of Temperature and Moisture
[24].

with various environmental and loading conditions. The ultimate success of analytical methods of predicting composite failure will depend upon the development of physical models of the failure process, as discussed previously.

Test Series	Specimen Condition	Axial Elastic Modulus E_{11} , GPa		Major Poisson's Ratio ν_{12}	
		Theory	Experiment	Theory	Experiment
<u>Tension</u>					
Quality Control	RTD	140	130	0.248	0.281
<u>Compression</u>					
Celanese Preliminary	RTD	140	110	0.248	0.344
Celanese Quality Control	RTD		113		--
Celanese	RTD		119		--
Celanese	RTW	140	111	0.247	0.335
Celanese	ETD	140	116	0.247	0.354
Celanese	ETW	139	114	0.247	0.327

Table 2: Axial Loading - Summary of Micromechanics Predictions Versus Experimental Data

Test Series	Specimen Condition	Transverse Elastic Modulus E_{22} , GPa		Minor Poisson's Ratio ν_{21}	
		Theory	Experiment	Theory	Experiment
<u>Tension</u>					
Quality Control Material Acceptance	RTD	9.3	10.1	0.016	
	RTD		9.5		--
<u>Compression</u>					
Celanese Quality Control	RTD	9.3	11.7	0.024	--
Celanese	RTD		10.0		--
Celanese	RTW	9.2	8.8	0.016	0.013
Celanese	ETD	8.6	11.1	0.015	0.031
Celanese	ETW	8.1	14.7	0.014	0.076

Table 3: Transverse Loading - Summary of Micromechanics Predictions Versus Experimental Data

The present Micromechanics analysis is such an approach. The ultimate goal is to be able to predict fatigue life. As previously stated, it is first necessary to be able to predict the static strength of a composite material adequately. Studies such as the present one are contributing much to the achievement of this first goal. The detailed presentations of Reference [1] indicate the extent to which this has been attained to date.

More detail is available from the Micromechanics program than can be readily measured experimentally. A sampling of this data will be included here. Much additional information has been omitted, but would be available to the user if needed.

The unidirectional laminate had an average fiber volume of 62.5 percent, which was modeled as a square array of fibers in the present study. Because of the symmetry of the regular (square) fiber packing, it is only necessary to study the stress state in one quadrant of the fiber and surrounding matrix. Thus, in the plots of local stress states, only one quadrant is shown. Also, because the local stresses in the matrix and at the fiber-matrix interface are of primary interest here, the stress distributions in the fiber have been omitted for clarity. These stresses are available from the analysis, however, and are stated where pertinent to the discussion.

The finite element grid used to model the first quadrant consisted of 230 constant strain triangular elements, the first 80 modeling the fiber and the remaining 150 elements modeling the surrounding matrix material. A grid of this degree of detail was found to give excellent accuracy for the present application.

All of the AS/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composites were cured at 177°C (350°F). During the subsequent cooldown to room temperature, thermal residual stresses were therefore developed in the composite due to the mismatch of the thermal expansion coefficients of the constituents (see Table 1). Thus, all of the composites, at the start of the preconditioning process, already contained internal stresses. These were predicted by the Micromechanics analysis. The analysis takes into account the fact that the matrix properties are continually changing during the cooldown process, as indicated in Figure 4.

Both tensile and compressive tests, in both the 0° and 90° directions, were conducted on the unidirectional laminate in the room temperature dry state.

If the curing residual stresses had not been present, the composite response, including the internal stress state, would be the same in tension and compression since the fiber and matrix material properties are assumed to be the same in tension and compression. Thus, it is of interest to look at the differences the thermal residual stresses create when the composite is subsequently loaded.

Figure 5 indicates the interface stresses present at an axial tensile applied stress of 1.65 GPa (240 ksi), the level at which first failure is predicted to occur. The average measured experimental value in tension was 1.62 GPa. Failure is predicted to occur due to the simultaneous occurrence of the 3.10 GPa (450 ksi) ultimate strength of the fiber being exceeded, and both the axial tensile strength and the octahedral shear strength of the matrix surrounding the fiber being exceeded. Thus, the cause of the "shattering" of these composites at failure, as noted experimentally [1], is obvious.

The predicted elastic modulus is 140 GPa (20.3 Msi), the average experimental value being 130 GPa. The experimental averages were for only two specimens, however. The higher of the two measured modulus values was 135 GPa. Thus, the agreement is quite satisfactory. The predicted major Poisson's ratio was 0.248, the lower of the two measured values being 0.262. Thus, the Micromechanics analysis gives reasonable predictions for axial tension. These and all other numerical comparisons for the various loading conditions are summarized in Tables 2 and 3.

The internal stress states at the fiber-matrix interface at failure presented in Figure 5, when compared with those present in the as-fabricated state, are higher, but not significantly so. In particular, the compressive normal stress at the interface has increased, due to the larger Poisson's ratio of the matrix relative to that of the fiber (see Table 1).

Figure 5
Stresses at the Fiber-Matrix Interface in a Unidirectional Composite Subjected to 1.65 GPa (240 ksi) Longitudinal Tension in a Room Temperature, Dry Condition.

The principal stresses throughout the matrix at failure are higher than prior to the axial tensile loading, as would be expected, but the distributions are not changed significantly. The maximum principal stresses in the transverse plane and the principal stresses in the axial direction are shown in Figure 6. The octahedral shear stress distribution is not included here, for brevity; the highest values occurred in the regions of closest fiber spacings, the concentration being slightly higher than that for the as-fabricated state.

The Micromechanics analysis predicts the unidirectional laminate to fail at an applied axial compressive stress of -1.96 GPa (-284 ksi), due to compressive failure of the fibers. However, the average measured failure stress was only -1.40 GPa, using a Celanese test fixture and five specimens. Thus, the predicted compressive failure stress is too high. This is not unexpected, however, since the observed failure modes included failure microbuckling, which is not accounted for in the analysis.

The predicted composite modulus is 140 GPa (the same as for tensile loading since the stiffnesses of the constituents were assumed to be the same in tension and compression, as previously noted). The measured modulus averaged 110 GPa for the five test specimens, with one value being 122 GPa. Thus, it appears that the compressive modulus of the unidirectional AS/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite is slightly lower than the tensile modulus. It should also be noted that the fiber axial modulus of 220 GPa (32 Msi) used in the Micromechanics analysis (Table 1) is an average value. The specific AS graphite fibers contained in the present specimens could have had an axial modulus slightly lower than 220 GPa, but still within the acceptance limits. This possibility is strongly suggested by the theory versus experiment comparisons of the axial tensile data; the axial modulus should be closely predicted by a rule of mixtures approximation (140 GPa in the present case). The Micromechanics prediction agrees with this value while the experimental value was only 130 GPa.

The predicted major Poisson's ratio of 0.248 compares adequately with the measured value of 0.344 .

The general shapes of the interface stress distributions at failure for the axial compressive loadings were similar to those shown in Figure 5 for the axial tensile loadings and thus are not included here. The magnitudes were only about 40 percent as high, however. Actually, the interface stresses increased under tensile loading, as previously discussed, while they decreased under compressive loading. In both cases they were relatively low, however, and the highest normal stress was compressive. Thus, it is not expected that the interface stresses contributed to the initial failure.

Figure 6
Matrix Stresses in a Unidirectional Composite Subjected to 1.65 MPa (240 ksi) Longitudinal Tension in a Room Temperature, Dry Condition.

The maximum principal stresses in the transverse plane and the axial principal stresses, at failure under an applied axial compressive stress, are presented in Figure 7. The compressive loading reduces the transverse principal stress induced by curing by about half, and reverses the sign of the axial principal stress, from tension to compression. That is, the matrix stresses, including those at the interface, are less severe at the applied axial compressive stress of -1.96 GPa than before the load is applied. This implies, of course, that the composite failure must be due to fiber compressive failure, which the Micromechanics analysis predicts. That is, at an applied stress of -1.96 GPa, the fiber compressive stress is -3.1 GPa, the ultimate value assumed in the analysis (see Table 1). It should be noted, however, that this fiber strength was measured in tension; the axial compressive strength of AS graphite fibers is not known, not being a readily measured property.

Similar micromechanical analyses were made of the transverse loadings, as well as for all of the other environmental conditions. Significant influences of moisture preconditioning and elevated test temperature were identified. These are discussed in detail in Reference [1]; space limitations do not permit a full presentation here. The $[\pm 45]$ and $[0_{16}/(\pm 45)_5/90_4]_c$ laminates were also analyzed in detail, the results being included in Reference [1] also.

a) Maximum Principal Stress in Transverse Plane (MPa)

b) Axial Stress (MPa)

Figure 7
Matrix Stresses in a Unidirectional Composite Subjected to 1.96 MPa (284 ksi) Longitudinal Compression in a Room Temperature, Dry Condition.

CONCLUSION

The present study represented a very thorough and rigorous test of the University of Wyoming's Micromechanics analysis. The analytical predictions of stiffness properties were found to be quite accurate. Considerable insight was also provided as to why certain failure modes observed in the SEM investigation occurred. Although more work needs to be done in incorporating an improved failure criterion, the predicted composite ultimate stresses did indicate general agreement with what was observed experimentally. In those cases where there was a large discrepancy, the reasons were explainable.

In certain isolated cases, the predicted trends in stiffness properties with increasingly severe environmental conditions did not correspond to what was measured experimentally. For example, the transverse elastic modulus of the unidirectional laminate was predicted to decrease slightly (Table 3), as would be expected since this is a matrix-dominated property and the modulus of the matrix was shown experimentally (Figure 4) to decrease. However, the experimentally measured composite modulus increased with temperature. A possible conclusion is that this points up the difficulty in experimentally determining this particular property accurately under hygrothermal conditions using present techniques. The same conclusions can be made in terms of the minor Poisson's ratio values of Table 3. This obviously is a

difficult property to measure because of its small magnitude for these composites.

The presence of normal scatter in the experimental data is suggested in the axial elastic modulus results of Table 2. The Micromechanics theory predicts a very slight decrease in this property with increasingly severe environmental conditions, this being a fiber-dominated property. The experimental data indicate no clear trend, the scatter in data being greater than the actual range of the expected variation.

These types of comparisons form the basis for the conclusion that an analytical prediction technique which is based upon fundamental physical principles, as the present Micromechanics analysis is, can be very useful in establishing trends in properties which are difficult to measure accurately.

One further conclusion which has been demonstrated in this study is that an analysis, once it has been demonstrated to be of acceptable accuracy, can be used to predict properties under other conditions as well, with only spot experimental checks being made to maintain confidence. Correspondingly, the analysis predicts all of the properties directly, while a significant number of different tests need to be performed to do the same experimentally. For example, the composite coefficients of thermal expansion and moisture expansion were not measured in the present study; yet they were automatically predicted.

With continued refinement, the Micromechanics analysis is expected to become a very powerful tool in predicting unidirectional ply performance, including the occurrence of local failure mechanisms such as matrix microcracking, fiber-matrix interface debonding, longitudinal splitting, and fiber microbuckling. Already it has been demonstrated to be a very simple and reliable way of estimating those ply properties which have not been measured for a particular composite, or of determining the influence of process variations and environmental conditions without resorting to an extensive experimental program.

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